

POLICY BRIEF

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NUCLEAR WEAPONS AND AUTONOMOUS SYSTEMS: EVEN CLOSER TO MIDNIGHT?

Author: Larlecianne Piccolliⁱ

POLICY STATEMENT

"We are 90s from midnight". On January 24th, 2023, for the first time in history, the "Doomsday Clock"ⁱⁱ reached its closest threshold to midnight since its creation. The war between Russia and Ukraine and the risk of a nuclear escalation of the conflict, intentional, accidental, or miscalculated, constitute a fundamental point for the establishment. It is also vital to consider disruptive innovations' weight in this determinationⁱⁱⁱ.

While the conflict in Eastern Europe amplified the possibility of using nuclear weapons (tactical nukes – in operational terms on the battlefield, and strategic – considering the strain of the nuclear regime among the nuclear powers), it has also validated the relevance of high-tech weapons. Both sides use armed drones and precision-guided munitions as significant disruptive resources in the conflict's conduct and management. That indicates the continuous development of new military technologies and the need to assess their impact on strategic relations between countries.

In this way, in addition to the current conflict serving as a backdrop, this Policy Brief seeks to extrapolate its thresholds, intending to gather initial information about disruptive military technologies, namely, nuclear weapons and Lethal Autonomous Weapon Systems (LAWS), alerting to the risk (of catastrophic effects) of their joint use.

BACKGROUND

Technological innovations gradually acquired a decisive role in the conduct of military strategies. In the 20th century, the military technological imperative, translated into the domain of the air (through the Air Force and the development of rockets) and the advent of nuclear weapons, became fundamental for military strategies' evolution. The technological transition, imputed not only to nuclear weapons but also to the synthesis of technology and knowledge – elucidated in the delivery vehicles of nuclear weapons and new strategic weapons – was consolidated as a design of constitutive elements of the relationship (polarity) between the countries. Nuclear weapons per se are not the only determining factor in the power hierarchy between states. In addition to that is the capacity for technological development, capacities that guarantee countries' discretion over warheads, delivery vectors, space control, space management, guidance, and accuracy of their systems.

The 21st century brought a new wave of technological strength widely embraced by the war industry. Artificial Intelligence (AI) advances include the development of smart munitions (using heat sources, laser beams, and geopositioning signals) and robotizing entire weapons systems programmed to hit enemy targets. The technological imperative now runs through the domain of AI and its application to generating war instruments that replace the masses of human armies. Is to say, taking the form of armed drones and other remote control devices, allowing humans to be physically absent from the battlefield (1), implying a reduction in the decision-making threshold for involvement in armed conflict.

Nuclear weapons: Atomic energy is the source of power for nuclear reactors and nuclear weapons, generated from the breaking/fission (fission bomb) or joining/fusion (thermonuclear bomb) of atoms. In the equation from Albert Einstein's studies of relativity theory, a small amount of matter can be converted into a large amount of energy, the key to nuclear weapons' massive power. In this way, the fundamental difference between conventional and nuclear weapons is the potency of their explosive capacity^{iv} since both rely upon their effectiveness in the destructive force of the explosion or shock wave. It should be noted that the nuclear explosion produces temperatures much higher than the conventional one, been responsible for severe burns and fires, as well as highly harmful radioactive rain (2) (3).

As Buzan and Hansen (4) stated, nuclear weapons provided additional destructive power capabilities never seen before in military history. The advent of atomic energy weapons and the evolution of their delivery vehicles provided nuclear countries with strategic capabilities, elevating them to the position of nuclear power. Evaluating the developments that nuclear weapons brought to military strategy is, obligatorily, analyzing the technological developments surrounding them. That is, concomitantly with the development of nuclear artifacts, it is crucial to analyze the development of delivery systems for the nukes. The production of delivery vehicles (engines, turbines, and so on), their consequences, and the systematization of spillover guarantee the objectivity of knowledge generation, serving as an envelope for the countries' capacity for action.

Ultimately, nuclear power is linked to technologies of conventional weapons systems, called the Nuclear Triad. Which consist of strategic bombers (air vector), intercontinental ballistic missiles (terrestrial vector), and ballistic missiles launched from submarines (maritime vector). The Nuclear Triad reduces the chances of an enemy destroying all of a country's nuclear capabilities in a first strike, ensuring responsiveness in a second strike. The reasoning guarantees common vulnerability, underpins Mutual Assured Destruction, embodies nuclear deterrence, and raises the powers to strategic stability.

As the Cold War unfolded, containment of the nuclear danger gained ground in the international debate, indeed becoming a prominent theme of the superpowers' (the United States of America - USA and the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics - USSR) agendas. Today, in addition to full knowledge of the political, moral, and ideological costs, nuclear weapons are still incorporated into the security and defense agenda of the United States and Russia.

The containment of the nuclear danger dictated (and dictated) the cooperation between the nuclear powers, leading them to sign several joint agreements to reduce and limit their nuclear arsenals. However, the increase in tensions between the countries led to the breakdown of foundational agreements, resulting in serious questions about the direction of global strategic stability and reducing the nuclear threshold.

Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems: LAWS are weapons systems that use software, sensor arrays, and computer algorithms to independently identify a target and employ lethal force to engage and destroy it (5). Such weapons, also known as lethal autonomous robots or killer robots, work without the intervention of a human operator, even being able to self-adapt to the circumstances of the environment to better respond to the reality of combat. Such Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems result from the interaction between military robotics and Artificial Intelligence (6).

It should be noted that, so far, there is no specific regulation on LAWS, with an extensive debate on definitions and concepts underway, covering a wide range of interpretations. The debate extends, for example, to the need to distinguish between automated versus autonomous weapons. The former is linked to systems previously programmed for their final objective, while the latter adjusts its programming to the environment encountered, which may lead to unpredictable outcomes (7).

The United States Department of Defense considers, within the framework of the Political Declaration on the Responsible Military Use of Artificial Intelligence and Autonomy, “autonomy” as the operability of a system without additional human intervention after its activation (8). Authors such as Peter Asaro (9), on the other hand, expand the threshold of coverage of law to judge more weapon systems as autonomous: “considering a class of autonomous weapon systems as any automated system that can initiate lethal force without the specific, conscious, and deliberate decision of a human operator, controller, or supervisor” (9).

Applied to the battlefield, the current generation of automated defense systems (e.g., THAAD and Patriot systems) can track and pursue hostile targets without human intervention. However, it cannot autonomously improve its ongoing performance. AI attributes this ability to new generations. In addition, the fusion of artificial intelligence technologies and advanced weapons would allow, in a simultaneous prospection in several combat zones, these systems to react and respond at machine speed, increasing the overall rhythm of combat. While AI powers early warning systems, allowing defense planners to more quickly and reliably identify and monitor threats, a lack of human judgment and oversight could significantly increase the risk of accidents and false alarms^v. This added to the critical response speed imputed by the machine, puts states under intense pressure to update and develop weapons systems, serving as a variable in the arms race spiral.

Therefore, the regulation of LAWS permeates technical-military aspects and legal and moral challenges, imposing a tactical and ethical dilemma on decision-makers.

FINDINGS

Based on this survey of preliminary information about technologies, nuclear weapons systems, and autonomous weapons systems, a search was done in the specialized literature for a system that would combine both. Materials and notes made on the Soviet *Perimetr* system were then retrieved. Based on the initial analyses, it is believed that *Perimetr* systematizes both technologies under debate, translating itself as an example to be considered.

The *Perimetr* system (*Mertvaya Ruka*, or "Dead Hand") was created from the Soviet Decree n. 695-227 of August 30th, 1974. The central objective is to guarantee the capability of nuclear retaliation even under highly adverse circumstances. In this sense, the nuclear command system is responsible for assessing the situation to which the country is exposed and making independent decisions. Thus, it allows Moscow to carry out a nuclear counterattack in situations of total absence of the institutional apparatus of the government (political and military leaders) responsible for the Command of the Nuclear Missile Forces or destruction of the communication system of the Command of Strategic Forces.

The system consists of a command ballistic missile (Design 15P011), whose payload is not for destructive artifacts but for issuing electronic commands. It is commissioned with radio transmitters that function as transmission lines, triggering other nuclear triad systems commissioned with nukes. The command IBCM flies over the country's territorial extension, not towards the enemy, sending launch commands to the other strategic forces. The autonomous system eliminates the human factor in the decision-making process of launching nuclear weapons (10).

The AI, which underpins the system, receives and analyzes data and information on seismic activity, radioactivity concentration in the atmosphere, atmospheric pressure, military radio frequency concentration, etc. When finding a position with ionizing solid radiation and electromagnetic waves, the system starts to compare it with the seismic instability database and, if identified as positive, starts the counterattack conditions analysis device, carried out in a series of steps (10) (11).

- (i) determination of whether or not there was a nuclear attack based on the technical information co-opted by the system;
- (ii) checking communication systems with General Staff: in case of positive contact, the system is disconnected; if not, send a request to the Strategic Forces Commander via the Kazbek command and control network;
- (iii) in the absence of a response, requests permission for other commanders subordinated to the Nuclear Forces to participate in decision-making;
- (iv) If it does not receive feedback, it initiates the implementation of the sequence of autonomous response actions – missile launch and frequency signal distribution for activation and launch of other nuclear weapons systems, imputing a response to the analyzed attack environment.

The conjuncture of the 1990s (political and economic crisis in the internal field and, in the external field, rapprochement with the West) led the Yeltsin government to suspend the development of the program, removing it from combat service. In the 2000s, under Putin's command, the process of restructuring the Armed Forces directed significant financial contributions to the Strategic Forces, including the Perimetr (10).

The autonomous nuclear response system, Perimetr, guarantees Moscow, to this day, the certainty of a nuclear counterattack, even in the absence of the entire hierarchy of human decision.

CONCLUSIONS

The international community is faced with a dual challenge. On the one hand, we are witnessing the deterioration of the strategic stability system due to the emptying of key nuclear agreements to contain the nuclear danger. See the unilateral withdrawal of the United States from the ABM and INF Treaties and the intention not to renew the New START Treaty by the United States and Russia. On the other hand, we face powerful technological advances, especially around Artificial Intelligence, which, when inserted into the military scope, become operational-tactical and legal-ethical challenges, lacking in elucidative regulation of possibilities and limits of LAWS use.

That said, it is believed that the disruptive military technologies worked on here (LAWS and nuclear weapons), whether used separately or jointly, can potentially raise instabilities and insecurity at a regional and global level. They also fuel a spiral of arms race and conflict escalation, posing a severe threat to global stability.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Taking into account the aspects presented above, some general recommendations are:

- (I) Faced with the alarming corrosion status of the political and military relations, whose escalation can so quickly culminate in an exchange of nuclear artifacts, it becomes relevant to reinstitutionalize a strategic relationship to eliminate the "incentives of a nuclear first strike."
- (II) Efforts to renew and/or reformulate the New START Treaty, for the time being, are the only bulwark of the global strategic stability regime. In this sense, it is crucial to advance negotiations in order to envisage the inclusion of topics such as the relationship (and definition) between offensive and defensive strategic weapons, conventional strategic weapons (definition and capabilities), the problem of speed (hypersonic); MIRV warheads.
- (III) Joint and coordinated work between countries to establish a structure for regulation and transparency in developing and commissioning autonomous military systems.

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ⁱ Ph.D. International Strategic Studies (UFRGS). President at ISAPE. Research Associate at Interagency Institute.

ⁱⁱ The "Doomsday Clock" was created in 1947 by scientists from the Bulletin of the Atomic Scientists to convey how close humanity is to self-destruction. It should be noted that the Bulletin of the Atomic Scientists was founded in 1945 by Albert Einstein, J. Robert Oppenheimer, and Eugene Rabinowitch, among other scientists who worked on the development of the first atomic weapons within the scope of the Manhattan Project, to alert the population and formulators of policies on artificial threats to its very existence. The Doomsday Clock symbolizes the world's vulnerability to the catastrophe of nuclear weapons, disruptive technologies, and climate change.

ⁱⁱⁱ For knowledge, climate change and biological threats are also variables considered in the analysis and determination of the Doomsday Clock. However, they will not be considered in this Policy Brief.

^{iv} For example, a 1Kt nuclear weapon produces the same amount of energy as 1,000 tons of TNT.

^v As in the "Able Archer" case in 1983, when a nuclear exercise by NATO forces took on such realistic contours that they raised Soviet nuclear forces to High alert, bringing the world to the edge of a nuclear conflict.